

Learned Constraint	Interpretation
sphn:hasSubjectAge(X, AgeGroup/Group2) ← hasDiagnosisCode(X, ICD9:2189)	If a patient has a diagnosis of ICD9 code 2189 (Leiomyoma of uterus, unspecified), then their age must be between 24 and 58.
sphn:hasSubjectAge(X, AgeGroup/Group2) ← hasDiagnosisCode(X, ICD9:66111)	If a patient has a diagnosis of ICD9 code 66111 (Secondary uterine inertia, delivered, with or without mention of antepartum condition), then their age must be between 24 and 58.
sphn:hasSubjectAge(X, AgeGroup/Group2) ← hasDiagnosisCode(X, ICD9:V2651)	If a patient has a diagnosis of ICD9 code V2651 (Tubal ligation status), then their age must be between 24 and 58.
sphn:hasSubjectAge(X, AgeGroup/Group3) ← hasDiagnosisCode(X, ICD9:61801)	If a patient has a diagnosis of ICD9 code 61801 (Cystocele, midline), then their age must be between 59 and 78.
sphn:hasSubjectAge(X, AgeGroup/Group2) ← hasDiagnosisCode(X, ICD9:2561)	If a patient has a diagnosis of ICD9 code 2561 (Other ovarian hyperfunction), then their age must be between 24 and 58.
sphn:hasAdministrativeGender(X, Female) ← hasDiagnosisCode(X, ICD9:V510)	If a patient has a diagnosis of ICD9 code V510 (Encounter for breast reconstruction following mastectomy), then their administrative gender must be female.
sphn:hasAdministrativeGender(X, Male) ← hasDiagnosisCode(X, ICD9:V502)	If a patient has a diagnosis of ICD9 code V502 (Routine or ritual circumcision), then their administrative gender must be male.
sphn:hasAdministrativeGender(X, Female) ← hasDiagnosisCode(X, ICD9:19881)	If a patient has a diagnosis of ICD9 code 19881 (Secondary malignant neoplasm of breast), then their administrative gender must be female.
sphn:hasAdministrativeGender(X, Female) ← hasDiagnosisCode(X, ICD9:E9322)	If a patient has a diagnosis of ICD9 code E9322 (Ovarian hormones and synthetic substitutes causing adverse effects in therapeutic use), then their administrative gender must be female.